

D6.1a PROJECT WEBSITE

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30 November 2022

Project Acronym	SUINK
Project Title	SUustainable self-charging power systems developed by INKjet printing
Grant Number	101070112
Project Coordinator	Estibaliz Gómez, Tekniker estibaliz.gomez@tekniker.es
Project Duration	1 September 2022 - 31 August 2026

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable No.	D6.1
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Work Package	WP6
Task	T 6.2
Lead Beneficiary	Greenovate! Europe
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	n/a
Due date of deliverable	30/11/2022
Actual submission date	30/11/2022

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author/Reviewer
1	29/11/2022	GIE	Elisa Casazza
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3			

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The URL for the SUINK project website (<https://www.suink.eu/>) was registered in September 2022. Before the full project website was launched, a provisional homepage was created under the above-mentioned URL. This temporary page included a short summary of the project's objectives, the link to the social media accounts and the contacts details of the project coordinator and communication manager.

The SUINK project website was launched on 30 November 2022 (M3), presenting all essential information about the project (such as, for instance, details about the expected results, partners, funding line, etc.). Project deliverables, press releases, and additional information materials, such as infographics, factsheets and videos, will be added throughout the project lifetime.

The SUINK social media accounts on **Twitter** ([@suink_eu](https://twitter.com/suink_eu)) and **LinkedIn** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/suink-project/>) were established prior to the kick-off meeting. The first post on both accounts was the press release announcing the start of the project in M1.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable aims to present the website of the SUINK project. The information outlined in this report will be complemented in M6 (February 2023) by the publication of the Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (D6.1b) that will then be updated annually.

2. WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The project web-portal – <https://www.suink.eu/>– is a reference point for the project communication and dissemination activities. The website was launched on 30 November 2022 (M3), in accordance with the Grant Agreement.

As of M1, a landing page was already available at the same address (www.suink.eu) with general information about the project and links to the already established SUINK [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts.

On 30 November 2022 (M3), the fully-fledged website of the SUINK project went live. The website has an engaging design (in line with the project’s visual identity developed at M1), and a user-friendly navigation menu.

The website currently presents the main objectives of the project, the expected results, the project partners and the related projects. It also provides links to the SUINK social media channels and publishes relevant updates, news, and communication materials.

As soon as more results will become available, the website will be updated to include regular updates about the project’s activities and act as the main platform to distribute any non-confidential material produced by the SUINK Consortium (e.g., scientific publications, webinars, videos, etc.).

The different sections of the website have the following content:

HOME	The homepage presents in a synthetic manner the project overview, with clickable links to the “Objectives”, “Partners” and “Resources” pages. The homepage also includes the latest news and events.
ABOUT	The “About” page presents the main elements of the projects, the objectives, the expected results, the Consortium partners, and the related projects.
RESOURCES	The “Resources” page will host all public deliverables, project factsheets, scientific publications and project videos.
NEWS & EVENTS	The “News & Events” page presents the latest updates about the project in terms of news and conferences.
MEDIA	The “Media” page presents downloadable material for the media, such as, for instance, communication materials, press releases, interviews, image gallery, etc.
CONTACT	The “Contact” page provides the contact details of the project coordinator and the communication manager.

3. CONCEPT AND TARGET GROUPS

The SUINK website aims to present the project in its full scope, documenting the developments, and communicating the project results to the relevant audiences in order to ensure their market uptake. The most important target groups are the following:

- **Industrial stakeholder community:** SMEs, large companies and industry associations from different sectors (automotive, textile, etc.), bio-chemical suppliers (additives for adjusting inks rheology) and sensor systems designers and manufacturers.
- **End-users (consumers of electronic devices):** the European citizens will be the final users of the project results, aiming to create healthier and more comfortable living environments.
- **Governmental and non-profit organisations:** Organisations and research institutes focusing on circular economy and social wellbeing.
- **Scientific community:** researchers in the field of nanomaterials, inks, binders, manufacturing processes and flexible electronics.

A more detailed stakeholder mapping will be presented in deliverable 6.1b “Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation” that will be submitted in M6.

4. ANNEX 1: IMAGES OF THE SUINK WEBSITE

4.1 Screenshot of the temporary page (live from M1-M3)

4.2 Screenshot of SUINK website home page

4.3 Screenshots of the “About” page

The challenge:

Today a modern car is equipped with over 60 sensors to monitor essential aspects such as temperature, oil pressure, emission levels, speed, etc. As autonomous and electric vehicles gain popularity, this number is only anticipated to rise. However, all of these sensors require electricity. At the moment, this is provided through cables that connect the sensors to the vehicle's battery, but this adds undesired weight and undermines the overall reliability of the vehicle.

In addition, to be in line with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the next generation of functional electronics must include new sustainability elements across their entire lifecycle:

Design: conventional electronic materials are often made of platinum, palladium, gold, copper, iron, etc. However, the sourcing of these materials (many of them classified as Critical Raw Materials) is often associated with severe human rights, environmental and geopolitical risks.

Manufacturing and use: manufacturing processes must become more energy-efficient, produce less waste, consume fewer resources, and emit fewer pollutants. Therefore, the use of power devices integrated with energy harvesting and storage systems - the so-called self-charging power systems (SCPS) - is needed.

End of life: electronic waste is one of the fastest growing waste streams worldwide, contributing to the release of toxic pollutants in the environment and the loss of valuable resources. New practices are, therefore, needed to make sure that electronic products are collected and recycled to a high standard.

The solution:

SUINK aims to develop green solutions to produce innovative sensors able to create their own energy rather than needing electricity from the vehicle's battery.

These self-charging power systems (SCPS) will be based on the combination of biobased, conductive, dielectric, and piezoelectric inks that will be applied by inkjet printing on biobased flexible surfaces.

These innovative power systems will rely on sustainable elements, including a piezoelectric energy generator, to harvest electrical energy from mechanical vibrations, and a rectifying system as a connection circuit with a supercapacitor as an energy storage component.

This innovative technology will be applied to produce temperature, humidity, and strain sensors used in the automotive sector, exploiting vibrations from the moving vehicle as a source of energy. Further applications will include the development of a new recyclable energy-harvesting textile material to be used in vehicles' interiors.

By reducing the weight of components, the SUINK project will contribute to increase the productivity and energy efficiency of the automotive industry, following a fully circular economy approach: from design to the end-of-life of products, implementing new recyclability and reusability protocols.

Expected results: To contribute to Europe's green and digital transformation, SUINK will develop:

1.

Novel sustainable biobased conductive and dielectric inks printable by inkjet printing.

2.

Functional piezoelectric poly(lactic acid) inks or film.

3.

Printed piezoelectric harvesting system based on piezoelectric poly(lactic acid) layers.

4.

Non-toxic printed supercapacitor integrated with the rectifying circuit.

5.

Flexible and printed electronic systems integration on different materials (textile, composites and polymers).

6.

Circular solutions and recycling strategies for plastics or composites with integrated electronics.

4.4 Screenshots of the “Resources” page

Scientific publications

Scientific test

Donec laoreet erat neque, sed lobortis ligula ultrices id. Proin scelerisque, turpis in interdum efficitur, orci ligula faucibus lacus, in blandit sapien ex sit amet purus. Donec turpis justo, dictum sit amet urna quis, lobortis egestas eros. Suspendisse congue rhoncus justo id tincidunt

[Download](#)

4.5 Screenshots of the “News & Events” page

News & Events

News

SUINK project launched to contribute to Europe's green and digital transformation
11/28/2022

The SUINK project aims to develop innovative green solutions to supply power to a wide range of sensors for the automotive sector. Tekniker and Greenovate! Europe are glad to announce the launch

[Read More](#)

Odio enim et illo assumenda minima eveniet
11/13/2022

Id sequi sequi aut repellendus. A dolorum alias repellendus minima odio perferendis delentis. Et doloreque ut animi atque molestias. Et quis dolor placeat. Recusandae quae perspiciatis veritatis cupiditate fugiat explicabo.

[Read More](#)

Hic esse natus consequatur voluptates alias
11/13/2022

Dolorum. Voluptatem veniam.

[Read More](#)

Soluta rem provident totam quod assumenda
11/13/2022

Qui provident odio magnam. Aut adipisci rerum omnis.

Tenetur et esse odio
11/13/2022

Dolor sit voluptatem. Illo ducimus voluptas quos.

Delectus quibusdam sunt quasi doloremque assumenda
11/13/2022

Optio debitis qui eveniet. Pariatur similique qui.

Upcoming Events

December 7, 2022

VDMA, Lyoner Straße 16, Frankfurt, Germany

OE-A and EPoSS workshop on Functional Electronics for Green and Circular Economy

[Read More](#)

Past Events

No events

4.6 Screenshots of the “Media” page

The screenshot shows the 'Media' page of the Suink website. The header is teal with the Suink logo on the left and navigation links (About, Resources, News & Events, Media, Contact) on the right. Below the header is a dark blue bar with the word 'Media' in white. The main content area is light blue and features a section titled 'Media resources'. This section contains two grey boxes: 'Press Releases' with a 'Download 167 KB' button, and 'Communication Resources' with the text 'Logo and the visual guidelines' and a 'Download 116 B' button.

Image Gallery

SUINK Consortium

SUINK Consortium

4.7 Screenshot of the “Contact” page

The screenshot shows the 'Contact' page of the Suink website. The page has a teal header with the Suink logo on the left and navigation links for 'About', 'Resources', 'News & Events', 'Media', and 'Contact' on the right. The 'Contact' link is highlighted. Below the header is a dark teal banner with the word 'Contact' in white. The main content area is light teal and features three sections: 'Project Coordinator' with Estibaliz Gómez, 'Communications' with Elisa Casazza, and 'Social media' with LinkedIn and Twitter icons. Each contact section includes a 'Send message' button. A large, stylized Suink logo graphic is positioned on the right side of the contact information.

Suink About Resources News & Events Media [Contact](#)

Contact

Project Coordinator:

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Communications:

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Social media:
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